

**THE
MASSLESS
GRAVITON-BASED
QUANTUM GRAVITY
IN
4-DIMENSIONAL
SPACETIME**

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APRIL 23 2025

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EINSTEIN FIELD EQUATIONS

"The supreme goal of every theory is to make the irreducible basic elements as simple and as few as possible without having surrender the adequate representation of simple datum of experience"
-Albert Einstein

The Einstein field equations (EFE) describe how matter and energy in the Universe influence the curvature of spacetime, which we perceive as gravity.

The mathematical form:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \kappa T_{\mu\nu}$$

$G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor that represent the curvature of spacetime.

Λ is the cosmological constant associated with dark energy and expanding Universe.

$g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor describing the geometry of spacetime.

κ is the Einstein gravitational constant

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = 2,077 \times 10^{-43} \frac{1}{N}$$

G is the Newton's gravitational constant, which qualifies the strength of gravity in Newton's law of gravity.

c is the velocity of light in vacuum.

$T_{\mu\nu}$ is stress-energy tensor or energy-momentum tensor that encapsulates the density and flux of energy and momentum in spacetime. It is bridge between matter-energy content and the curvature of spacetime. Stress-energy tensor provides a comprehensive description of how energy and momentum are distributed and interact with the fabric of spacetime.

The Einstein gravitational constant κ , is a fundamental in Einstein's Theory of General Relativity. It tells us the relationship between the geometry of spacetime and energy-matter content with in that spacetime. κ serves as "proportionality factor" that determines how matter and energy influence the curvature of spacetime.

κ scales the contribution of the stress -energy tensor in shaping the geometry described by Einstein tensor.

"Spacetime tells matter how to move; matter tells spacetime how to curve"
- John Archibald Wheeler

Einstein gravitational constant κ quantifies the coupling between energy matter content and the curvature of spacetime. It has a essential role in General Relativity which describes the dynamics of gravitational interaction.

METHODS

THE EINSTEIN'S FIELD EQUATION

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

EINSTEIN'S GRAVITATIONAL CONSTANT

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = 2,077 \times 10^{-43} \frac{1}{N}$$

OTHER CONSTANTS USED:

$$\text{Velocity of light in vacuum, } c = 299792458 \frac{m}{s}$$

$$\text{Newton's universal gravitational constant, } G = 6,67430 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2}$$

$$\text{Reduced Planck constant, } \hbar = 1,054571800 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$$

$$\text{Planck constant, } h = 6,62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$$

$$\text{Boltzmann constant, } k_B = 1,380649 \times 10^{-23} \frac{m^2 kg}{s^2 K}$$

$$\text{Planck length, } l_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}} = 1,61625518 \times 10^{-35} \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Planck mass, } m_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}} = 2,17643424 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Planck time, } t_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}} = 5,39124760 \times 10^{-44} \text{ s}$$

$$\text{Planck area, } l_p^2 = \frac{\hbar G}{c^3} = 2,6121 \times 10^{-70} \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Planck volume, } l_p^3 = \left(\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} = 4,2217 \times 10^{-105} \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Planck momentum, } m_p c = \frac{\hbar}{l_p} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^3}{G}} = 6,5249 \frac{kg m}{s}$$

$$\text{Planck energy, } E_p = m_p c^2 = \frac{\hbar}{t_p} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}} = 1,9561 \times 10^9 \text{ J}$$

$$\text{Planck force, } F_p = \frac{E_p}{l_p} = \frac{\hbar}{l_p t_p} = \frac{c^4}{G} = 1,2103 \times 10^{44} \text{ N}$$

$$\text{Planck pressure, } P_p = \frac{c^7}{\hbar G^2} = \frac{E_p}{l_p^3} = 4,633 \times 10^{113} \text{ Pa}$$

$$\text{Planck density, } \rho_p = \frac{m_p}{l_p^3} = \frac{\hbar t_p}{l_p^5} = \frac{c^5}{\hbar G^2} = 5,1550 \times 10^{96} \frac{kg}{m^3}$$

$$\text{Hubble constant, } H_0 (s^{-1}) = 2,18 \times 10^{-18} s^{-1} \text{ (Planck, 2018), } H_0 (s^{-1}) = 2,36 s^{-1} \text{ (SHOES, 2021)}$$

$$\text{Dark energy density, } \rho_{DE} = \frac{3H_0^2 \Omega_\Lambda c^2}{8\pi G} = 5,217 \times 10^{-10} \frac{J}{m^3}$$

$$\text{Cosmological constant, } \Lambda = \kappa \rho_{DE} = \frac{3H_0^2 \Omega_\Lambda}{c^2} = 1,08 \times 10^{-52} \frac{1}{m^2}$$

QUANTUM GRAVITY FIELD EQUATIONS

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{3\hbar c}{N\sqrt{N}lp^3 Egr} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\sqrt{6\Lambda}lp^2\lambda}{3\hbar c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{Ep3tp\lambda}{2\pi\hbar N\sqrt{N}lp^3} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{Ep3tp\lambda}{2\pi\hbar 2NPqlp^3} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{Pp3tp\lambda}{2\pi\hbar N\sqrt{N}} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{Pp3tp\lambda}{2\pi\hbar 2NPq} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{9Pp}{N\sqrt{N}Pq4\pi lp^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\hbar c}{NPq\frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3 Egr} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{96\pi^2}{\lambda^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi\hbar c N} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{24\pi}{Rs} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{4\pi Rs}{N Egr} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{6}{Rs^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{2\pi\hbar c}{N Egr^2} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{3H_0^2\Omega\Lambda}{c^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\lambda}{N Egr} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{6}{Nlp^2} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\sqrt{6\Lambda}lp^2\lambda}{3\hbar c} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{24\pi\hbar c}{\sqrt{N}lp^3 Fp\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\lambda}{NPq\frac{4}{3}\pi lp^3} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$\hbar = mbit c 2\sqrt{Nlp^2} = mbit c 2\sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}}$$

$$mbit = 7,465 \times 10^{-70} \text{ kg} \rightarrow Egr = mbit c^2 \rightarrow \lambda = \frac{\hbar c}{Egr}$$

DARK ENERGY DENSITY

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{\Lambda c^4}{8\pi G} = 5,217 \times 10^{-10} \frac{J}{m^3}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{N h c \Lambda}{\lambda^2}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{N E_{gr} \Lambda}{\lambda}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{Pq N \frac{4}{3} \pi l p^3 \Lambda}{\lambda}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{12 \pi \hbar c}{l p^2 \lambda^2}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{3 \hbar c}{4 l p^2 R s^2}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{3 \hbar c}{16 \pi l p^2 R^2}$$

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{3 \hbar c}{\lambda l p^3 \sqrt{N}}$$

QUANTUM COSMOLOGICAL INFLATION

$$G^{\mu\nu} + \frac{Pp^3 tp \lambda}{2\pi \hbar N \sqrt{N}} g^{\mu\nu} = \frac{Pp^3 tp \lambda}{2\pi \hbar 2 N Pq} T^{\mu\nu}$$

$$Ep = Pp lp^3 = mp c^2 \rightarrow Rmp = \frac{2Gmp}{c^2} = lp \rightarrow V1 = \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \rightarrow Psch = \frac{Ep}{\frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3} = 1,106 \times 10^{113} Pa$$

$$V2 = \frac{Ep}{\rho DE} \rightarrow \rho DE = \frac{2 mbit c^2}{\frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \sqrt{N}} \rightarrow V2 = \frac{mp \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \sqrt{N}}{2 mbit} = N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 = 3,76 \times 10^{18} m^3$$

$$N = \frac{6}{\Lambda lp^2} = 2,12 \times 10^{122} bit$$

$$A = 4\pi lp^2 N = \frac{24\pi}{\Lambda} = 6,98 \times 10^{53} m^2$$

$$Rsch = \sqrt{\frac{A}{4\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} = 2R = 2,357 \times 10^{26} m$$

$$M = \frac{Rsch c^2}{2G} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} Pq N 4\pi lp^2}{3\sqrt{N} c^2} = 1,587 \times 10^{53} kg \rightarrow mbit = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} Pq 4\pi lp^2}{3\sqrt{N} c^2} = \frac{M}{N} = 7,465 \times 10^{-70} kg$$

$$E = M c^2 = N mbit c^2 = Pq N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 = 1,426 \times 10^{70} J$$

$$G = \frac{Rc^2}{N mbit} \rightarrow R = \sqrt{\frac{N \pi lp^2}{4\pi}}$$

$$V3 = \frac{E}{\rho DE} = \frac{Pq N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3}{\rho DE} = N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \frac{\sqrt{N}}{2} = \frac{\lambda N lp^2}{6} = 2,74 \times 10^{79} m^3$$

$$lp^3 \rightarrow tp1 \rightarrow \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \rightarrow tp2 \rightarrow N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \rightarrow tp3 \rightarrow N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 \frac{\sqrt{N}}{2}$$

$$Pp = 4,633 \times 10^{113} Pa \rightarrow Pq = 3,79 \times 10^{51} Pa$$

$$\lambda = \frac{hc}{Egr} = 4\pi \sqrt{N lp^2} = 4\pi \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}}$$

MASS ENERGY EQUALS GRAVITATIONAL POTENTIAL

$$\sum (Egr) + \sum -\left(G \frac{M mbit}{R}\right) = 0$$

$$\sum (mbit c^2) + \sum -\left(Pq \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3\right) = 0$$

$$\sum (mbit c^2) + \sum Egr = 0$$

NEWTON'S GRAVITATION LAW

$$F = \left(G \frac{M1 m2}{r^2}\right)$$

$$G = \frac{\hbar c}{4 N mbit^2} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{3}{2\Lambda}} c^2}{N mbit} = \frac{\sqrt{N} lp c^4}{2 N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 Pq}$$

$$N1 = \frac{M1}{mbit}, N2 = \frac{m2}{mbit};$$

$$F = \frac{N1 N2 R Egr}{N r^2} = \frac{N1 N2 \frac{\sqrt{N} lp^2}{2} Egr}{N r^2} = \frac{N1 N2 \sqrt{\frac{3}{2\Lambda}} Egr}{N r^2} = \frac{N1 N2 \lambda Egr}{2 N \times 4 \pi r^2} = \frac{N1 N2 \hbar c}{N 4 r^2}$$

$$R = \frac{Rsch}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{N} lp^2}{2} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2\Lambda}} = \frac{\lambda}{8\pi} : \lambda = \frac{\hbar c}{Egr} = 4\pi \sqrt{N} lp^2 = 4\pi \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}}$$

BLACK HOLE THERMODYNAMICS

HAWKING TEMPERATURE

$$TH = \frac{\hbar c^3}{8\pi G Mx kB}; Nx = \frac{Mx}{mbit}, N = \frac{6}{\Lambda lp^2} \rightarrow TH = \frac{N Egr}{2\pi Nx kB} = \frac{Pq N \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3}{2\pi Nx kB} = \frac{3 Egr}{\pi lp^2 Nx kB \Lambda}$$

SCHWARZCHILD RADIUS

$$Rs = \frac{2GMx}{c^2} = \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} \frac{Nx}{N} = \sqrt{N lp^2} \frac{Nx}{N} = \frac{\sqrt{6\Lambda} Nx lp^2}{6} = \frac{\lambda Nx}{4\pi N}$$

SURFACE AREA OF THE BLACK HOLE

$$A = 4\pi Rs^2 = \frac{4\pi lp^2 Nx^2}{N^2} = \frac{24\pi Nx^2}{\Lambda N^2} = \frac{2\pi (Nx lp^2)^2 \Lambda}{3}$$

BEKENSTEIN-HAWKING ENTROPY

$$S_{BH} = \frac{kB c^3 A}{4\hbar G} = \frac{\pi kB Nx^2}{N} = \frac{\pi lp^2 Nx^2 kB \Lambda}{6}$$

BEKENSTEIN-HAWKING LUMINOSITY AS FUNCTION OF MASS

$$L = \frac{\hbar c^6}{15360\pi G^2 M^2} = \frac{Egr \sqrt{N} c}{80 \times 4\pi lp^2 Nx^2 lp \Lambda} = \frac{N c N Egr}{480 Nx^2 \lambda} = \frac{N c N Pq \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3}{480 Nx^2 \lambda}$$

SMALLER BLACK HOLES EMIT MORE RADIATION
AS BLACK HOLE RADIATES, IT'S ENTROPY DECREASES

TIME THAT BLACK HOLE TAKES TO DISSIPATE

$$tev = \frac{5120\pi G^2 M^3}{\hbar c^4} = \frac{80 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi lp^3 Nx^3 \Lambda}{\sqrt{N} c} = \frac{160 Nx^3 \lambda}{N^2 c}$$

TIME DEPENDENT SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \Psi(r, t) = \hat{H} \Psi(r, t)$$

POSITION SPACE WAVE FUNCTION

$$\Psi(r, t)$$

$$\Psi(r, t) = \Psi(r) T(t)$$

FUNCTION OF TIME, "THE PHASE FACTOR"

T

IN 3-DIMENSIONAL POSITION SPACE VECTOR (r) IS SPECIFYING POINT (x,y,z).

FUNCTION OF SPATIAL COORDINATES (Ψ)

$$x = r \sin \Theta \cos \Phi, \quad y = r \sin \Theta \sin \Phi, \quad z = r \cos \Theta$$

$$x = lp \sin \Theta \cos \Phi, \quad y = lp \sin \Theta \sin \Phi, \quad z = lp \cos \Theta$$

$$x = tp \sin \Theta \cos \Phi, \quad y = tp \sin \Theta \sin \Phi, \quad z = tp \cos \Theta$$

3D-SPATIAL POSITION SPACE COORDINATES (Ψ) CORRESPONDING TO GRAVITON

PLANCK SCALE SPATIAL INFORMATION: $\Psi(x,y,z)$

(Picture Wikipedia: Smite-Meister: Bloch sphere, 30 January 2009)

TIMESPACE QUANTUM

$$r = lp = tp$$

CELESTIAL HOLOGRAPHY

3D spatial information (x,y,z) of graviton (Ψ on Bloch sphere) in position spacetime (bulk) corresponding to entangled graviton α (on the 2-dimensional conformal boundary=Riemann sphere) is projected to 2D-holographic gravitational field point A.

Stereographic projection. Image: Jean-Christophe Benoist.

(Picture Wikipedia: Stereographic projection: Image:Jean-Christophe Benoist)

Conformal bound-like 2D-Riemann sphere surface picturing 2D-information projected to middle of 3+1-dimensional Penrose diagram (point A, no time)

$$D \text{ Bulk} = D \text{ Boundary} + 1$$

$$MASS : mbit(x, y, z) \text{ position space} \rightarrow 3D - BULK : -\frac{4}{3} \pi l p^3, \rightarrow 2D - BOUNDARY$$

Wheeler-DeWitt-equation defines spacetime and tensor network geometry.

$$\hat{H} \Psi (\text{universe}) = 0$$

Time is emergent distance between events.

HEISENBERG'S UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$$

$$\hbar = mbit \ c \ 2 \ Rsch = mbit \ c \ 2 \sqrt{N \ lp^2} = mbit \ c \ 2 \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}}$$

$$\Delta x \approx 1 \times 10^{-35} \ m \rightarrow 2D-BOUNDARY : \Delta x \approx 4 \ \pi \ lp^2 \ x \ X ? \rightarrow \Delta x \approx 2 \times 10^{26} \ m$$

$$\text{Reduced Planck constant : ACTION : } \hbar = mp \ c \ lp = mp \ c^2 \ tp = mbit \ c \ 2 \sqrt{N \ lp^2} = mbit \ c \ 2 \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}}$$

$$V \beta = \frac{lp^3}{N} = 1,9925 \times 10^{-227} \ m^3$$

$$l \beta = \frac{lp}{\sqrt[3]{N}} = 2,711 \times 10^{-76} \ m$$

$$t \beta = \frac{tp}{\sqrt[3]{N}} = 9,0409 \times 10^{-85} \ s$$

$$\text{ACTION : } \hbar \beta = mbit \ c \ l \beta = mbit \ c^2 \ t \beta = 6,0955 \times 10^{-137} \ Js$$

NO WAVE FUNCTION, JUST ACTION